

EVOLVING LEARNING SPACES

An Architectural response to changing educational practices

Indrajeet Sunil Ghule

Architect

indrajeetghule9@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

There has been a great evolution in education and learning style to which the spaces are trying to cater. Yet there are some areas where the architecture is not able to respond to the current educational needs. The existing classrooms are not able to cater to today's needs as the architecture is not responding. Thus, the process of teaching-learning is not able to evolve. The research concentrates on the study of the pre-university teaching-learning space (11th and 12th), as it is the threshold between school and university where the most crucial decisions are taken by students for their further studies. Thus, the research focuses to find the factors which have affected these learning spaces and how effectively these spaces can be improved through design. Furthermore, the research focuses on identifying crucial aspects to design these spaces, keeping in mind tomorrow's requirements. The study was carried out by conducting various surveys and measured drawings of classrooms. An attempt is made in the form of recommendations for the development of teaching-learning spaces.

KEYWORDS - education, evolution, teaching learning spaces, technology, spatial requirements

1 INTRODUCTION

Since we know the importance of education, it is also crucial to study the spaces where these activities are carried out. Educational Architecture is gone through various developments. The spaces are now different from what we had a few decades ago. Thus, the research deals with the study of these spaces and to understand their journey and how the factors have made these spaces change. For education, if subjects are the medium, then the classroom is the mode or the method. This thought provoked to study the teaching-learning spaces and how they have changed or adapted or whether they are the same.

Have you ever asked yourself, "Would I want to spend time as a student in my own classroom?" Perhaps this is the simplest question we can ask when considering all the 'elements' that goes into the physical and psychological elements of a classroom. We may all have varying ideas of what a classroom should look, feel, and sound like depending on our teaching style, previous experiences, or perhaps our principal's expectations. However, one thing remains constant for all students: the subconscious messages they receive upon entering the classroom by visually scanning the space.[2](Bennett September 22,2015)

What we are today is a gift given to us by our teachers and parents. The values, morals and all the learning have been blessed upon us in the temple called 'Classrooms'. We might not remember the logarithmic tables or the reactions of chemistry but today we do react to situations and scenarios by applying the knowledge we have learnt. Today we are standing on a platform where the education from our school is our foundation. And then comes a phase after school where one has to choose a career path, an important year in the life of a student, the gateway or the transit from schooling to becoming a professional - "The junior college 11th and 12th standard", an area where one makes crucial decisions for his career. The research focuses on the 11th and 12th standard classroom teaching-learning with students from Science, Commerce and Arts discipline.

1.1 Background

The Indian educational system has evolved through a great wisdom which has originated from the Vedas and has still kept our culture intact. From the study of our Educational system and architecture it is very evident that the transition from schooling to college, a student has to cross a threshold called as the Junior college, the 11th and 12th Standard. This threshold is a stepping stone between the schools where the foundation is built to the further university studies. The Research paper focuses on this threshold where a significant development is needed. The schools and the senior colleges are progressing in terms of development, but this pre-university phase where a student takes the most crucial decision for this career yet remains stagnant.

Today we see a lot of technological changes, Architecture also has evolved with time, but there are some spaces which have not changed remarkably as expected, the classrooms, where the future of tomorrow is getting moulded . Thus, my research focuses to find the factors which have affected these learning spaces and what can be done to improve these spaces and what aspects are crucial to design these spaces which can help a designer to create spaces for today, keeping in mind tomorrow's requirements.

Schools are influenced by political and social movements, new technologies and trends, the growing awareness of what makes us learn better and thus our notions of what makes a great school are constantly shifting and adapting to new ideas. Yet, we are still surrounded by the schools that matched the ideologies of over a century ago.[1](Baker January 2012)

2 EVOLUTION OF EDUCATION AND ARCHITECTURE

2.1 Literature Review: History of Education in India- J.P.Naik, Syed Nururllah [3](Syed Nurullah 1943)

The book explains how the educational journey from the Vedic age started. The main focus is on influence of the British policies made in the education system. According to linguistic states, more emphasis was given to the formation of universities during this period. Today the method of teaching-learning is mostly derived from this system formed during the British era.

The usual centres of learning were either some king's capital such as Kanauj, Dhar, Mithila, or Djayani, or holy places such as Varanasi, Ayodhya, Kanchi or Nasik and places like Nalanda, Gandhara and Takshashila. In addition to Buddhist Viharas (monasteries), there sprang up Hindu 'mathas' (monk's residences) and temple colleges, and agrahara villages (where spiritual and pedagogic functions are performed by learned Brahmins) in different parts of the country. It is noticed that the growth of temples in India was an indication of growth of education. [5]Thus, the table 2-1 clearly explains how the spaces have evolved with the changing educational pattern. This study gives a holistic understanding.

2.2 Essential of the classrooms today

For learning spaces to be purposeful and appealing, they should be designed around the things that are fundamental to all humans, their experiences and motivations. In addition, they should consider the unique culture of students and faculty on each campus. Within these spaces, the surroundings, furnishings and tools should work in concert to provide an optimal experience of learning and teaching, and should fluidly change as the needs of students and faculty evolve.[3](Miller 2015)

A classroom has to be sensitively thought, the need of the user how a small element can change the entire work flow or might just become a barrier in the entire process of learning. The visual stimulation, arrangement of furniture and natural light and ventilation is the basic need; this will promote more users to be in that space. The classroom has to become a memory which will help students recall the lessons learnt. Information technology is radically changing the ways that we build and conceive of schools, as traditional spatial configurations for presentation are no longer as

necessary as they once were, and technologies allow for new learning modes and practices. Major technological advances in energy-related building systems are being made every year, as the sustainable building industry grows and gains acceptance.[1] (Baker, January 2012)

Table 2-1 explains the case examples selected ranging from 1885 to 2006 to understand the journey. The area of the classrooms and how they balance the number of students also is understood. The locations of the colleges also have different lifestyles and cultures which has a different impact on the psychology of the students.

Table 2-1-Evolution of Education and Architecture (Source:-Author, Developed from literature review History of Education in India –J.P.Naik, Syed Nurullah)

Period	Teaching style	Space	Learnings and Methods	No. of Years engaged	Socio -Economic
Vedic Civilization (2000-800 B.C. period)	Gurukul and Ashramas Figure 2.1 Source :- Om Ashram	Pathshalas Conducted by Brahmin acharyas at their residences.	Rigveda, Samveda, Atharvaveda, Yajurveda, Etc. (based on the Upanishads).	The Education started from age of 7 and continued upto the students masters their subject.	The education was mostly taken by the affluent class of Kshatriyas like the kings, landlords. The Brahmin class contributed in imparting knowledge to these classes which helped them to earn a livelihood.
Gupta and Harsha Period(period) 4 th -8 th century	Similar like the Vedic age but with more importance towards education	Acharyas residence, universities for higher knowledge.	 Figure 2.2 Nalanda University	Buddhist learning.	Takshashila international reputation, This institution included special institutions of law, medicine and military science. Significant advancement in the field of Indian sciences, mathematics and astronomy.
Indigenous Education till the beginning of 19 th century	Gurus Residence In form of a gurukul. Gurus were invited to the house to select the student.	The spaces were defined according to the type of teaching.	School started sharp at 6 am. The first student to come is given an honour by the stamp of Goddess Saraswati on his hand; the students who were delayed were severely punished.	5-7 years or upto the wish of the students and his wish to learn.	The people with good financial condition could allow long term of teaching, others had to quit due to the financial issues. Even the masters suffered from financial Crunch that laid to decay the condition of these schools.
Influence of East India Company 1813 onwards	 Figure 2.3 Charity schools	Classroom originated as a built space Intention to spread Christianity.	Teaching of philanthropic nature. The Origin of primary, secondary type system in India Charity schools were built.	From the age of 5 and students were promoted to seek foreign education.	The Education focussed the affluent class. While the missionaries focused on the primary education in their mother tongue.
1813-33	Education through local languages.	Colleges and schools.	Formation of subjects with grouping science, commerce, arts.	Age of 5 till 18	The British were more focused over ruling the country and spreading their ideals.
1921 onwards	The system was handed to Indians	Adopting the ideas of British and incorporating their system.	Primary, Secondary, Professional Colleges and schools, Art Colleges.	—	To spread knowledge to all the sects, this system was oriented towards male. Formation of Aided and Un-aided institutes.
Establishment of universities	Influence of diarchy	Then the independence era and spreading education to all.	Similar pattern as used by the British.	—	Importance given to all the lower classes and also to women Currently, India holds the largest youth population Source: UN report 2014.

3 UNDERSTANDING OUR CLASSROOMS:-CASE EXAMPLES

Study of classrooms was carried out based on the parameters such as Physical Social and Psychological. The case examples were shortlisted from Pune, Maharashtra. The Author maintains due respect to confidentiality of the case studies and hence the names have not been mentioned.

Table 3-1- Statistical Comparison between the Case examples (Source:-Author)

	Case 1	Case 2	Case 3	Case 4
Reason of Selection	One of the renowned and old heritage school in Pune	An institute with good academic reputation but lacks infrastructure	School located in a cosmopolitan area established recently	A top IB school attempting to impart education adapting digital medium.
Establishment	1885	1986	2006	2006
Courses	Science, Commerce, Arts	Science, Commerce	Science, Commerce	Science, Commerce
Student Teacher ratio	1:100	1:100	1:80	1:20
Area of Classroom	108 sq.m	85sq.m	77sq.m	45sq.m
Area per student	1.08 sq.m/student	0.85sq.m/student	0.95sq.m/student	2.25sq.m/student
Possibility outdoor classroom	Open spaces need buffer if planning for outer.	No availability of space.	Space available but not utilised for outdoor learning.	Adaptive usage of transition spaces for outdoor classroom.
Acceptance for Technology	Yes, Use of LCD projectors.	They want technology to be a part of their classrooms.	Facilities not provided in the classes but can be well implemented.	Use of technology and also promote students towards e- learning.
Sample Size for primary survey	Two classroom consisting 100 students each and their concerned subject teachers	Two classroom consisting 100 students each and their concerned subject teachers	Two classroom consisting 80 students each and their concerned subject teachers	Three classroom consisting 20 students each and their concerned subject teachers

3.1 Case 1:-

The most renowned college with a great history which has molded many great people for the society. The overall furniture arrangement is well spaced out; each student can see the board and the teacher comfortably. On asking the students about their class, they are comfortable with the overall environment. The light quality and the soothing colour scheme have helped them to settle into this new environment comfortably. Also, the student-teacher ratio is dealt by providing tiered seating where each one has a contact with their teacher. However, the classroom faces issues in terms of acoustics.

Fig.3.1- Plan and Section of Classroom Case 1 Junior college (Source: - Author)

3.2 Case 2: -

An institute which has a good reputation but unfortunately lacks infrastructure. The issue of the infrastructure is becoming a limitation for the teachers for adopting innovative learning methods. Even the students are getting demotivated as they are being subjected into an uncomfortable environment. There is no scope for light and ventilation as the classrooms are in an upper basement. The services haven't been thought for mechanical lighting and ventilation. The teachers find it difficult to manage the class.

Fig.3.2- Plan and Section of Classroom Case 2 Junior college (Source:- Author)

3.3 Case 3: -

The institute dwells in the other part of the city with different culture and lifestyle (Pune camp.). The Classrooms lack good day lighting. The lecturer does not have any raised platform thus; the last benches get cut off from what is going inside the classroom. The students are also not happy with the overall furniture layout and commented that the classroom is not well ventilated. The Classroom is a typical layout which can be made into an interactive zone, but the student teacher ratio 1:80 becomes a limitation.

Fig.3-3- Plan and Section of Classroom Case 3 Junior college (Source:- Author)

3.4 Case 4:-

A top IB (International Baccalaureate) international school which has modern teaching learning styles still the roots are towards the traditions and culture of India. The success of this classroom is the student teacher ratio (1:20 max) which creates a bond with the teacher. This also helps the students in mental strengthening.

Fig.3-4- Plan and Section of Classroom Case 4 Junior college (Source:-Author)

3.4.1 An Overview

With 356 million people between the age of 10-24 years, India has the world's largest youth population according to UN report 2014. Thus, the colleges are trying to balance these ratios by in the existing infrastructure. An adaptive usage is done in the same space, which compromises on the learning process. The classrooms designed in the past are also trying to incorporate the new technologies which are becoming difficult. Due to the typical layout carried forward from years, the new learning skills have not been explored and the teaching and learning process have become mundane.

3.4.2 Users interpretations and opinion towards the whole scenario

The students and teachers were asked questions based on physical, social and psychological parameters. One of the questions asked was from the visuals below which would they prefer as their classroom and why?

3.5 Choice A (Source:-Artcobell)

Figure 3.6 Choice B (Source:-Artcobell)

Figure 3.7 Choice C

Figure 3.8 Choice D

The students and teachers mostly opted for A and C, the reason being the easy access to the teacher or vice versa. Many students also liked the A option as they had a direct contact with the teacher. The D option was least wanted as the users are irritated with typical arrangement. The B option was not liked even though the furniture is interesting because there is a disconnection between the student and the teacher.

Fig.3-9 Showing the choice what the students and teachers made. (Source: - Author)

Fig.3-10 Showing the rating done by students for the above categories (Source: - Author)

Refer Figure 3-9. Therefore; we infer that the students want the teacher to be very accessible for efficient learning. Students and teachers were also asked to grade their classrooms for light and ventilation, acoustics and comfort. Case 1 maintains an equal distribution but lacks in acoustics. The Case 2 lacks in all the factors. Case 3 lacks in light quality. Case 4 has maintained a very good balance between the classrooms and also the student teacher ratio. Refer Figure 3-10.

It can be concluded that since the tiered classrooms provide better eye contact they work well. In hall/room the depth of the classroom matters and the student teacher ratio plays an important role. The light aspect along with acoustics plays the key role in building an environment for lectures or activities. The urge of teaching – learning is very much present, but the spaces sometimes are not promoting the exchange. The users are not happy with the current typical arrangement. The need for creative classroom is very vital only then can the temples of knowledge flourish!

4 OUTDOOR CLASSROOMS

The survey revealed that the students and teachers also were in for outdoor learning. The teachers were concerned about the disturbance which as a designer can be taken as a challenge to deal with and get an outdoor learning space. While some teachers went ahead with the suggestions such as the trees can become a support where they can put the board. According to author, it is a collaborative initiative where a designer can allow the space to be designed by the teachers and students which will create more attachment towards the space.

Fig.0.1 Conceptual ideas (Source:- Author)

5 OTHER ASPECTS

Apart from the aspects of light, ventilation, acoustics; other aspects need to be understood are:-

- **Thinking (Teaching Style):**-To meet 21st century expectations, educators therefore need to depart from the ideas and pedagogies of yesterday and become bold advocates to develop the sorts of learning dispositions needed for our learners and their work futures. This means spending less time explaining through instruction and investing more time in experimental and error-tolerant modes of engagement.
- **Seating layout and design:**-This aspect varies from a person to person. According to Author a layout where each student can concentrate on the board and can easily approach a teacher, has a proper visibility to the board. Even where the teacher can understand each student at a glance is an ideal layout. The furniture also has to be designed to match the ergonomics. The seating should be just adequately comfortable otherwise one will not stay alert during the lectures.
- **Objects and Decoration:** - Busy classrooms with a lot of posters and walls with articles can sometimes be of distraction, a balance between the two is very essential so as to obtain a harmony in the space.

6 ANALYSIS:

- The important criteria while designing a classroom is the student-teacher ratio.
- For an Indian context, the tiered classrooms works very well in terms of visual connection and each student is able to see the board, thus creating no barriers in losing concentration.
- The limitation that comes with this configuration (tiered) is that the classroom cannot be used for informal activities. It also becomes a disciplined model.
- Tiers create a sort of discipline in the classroom.
- In the hall type configuration the raised platform creates a better connection between the student teacher, but a deep classroom doesn't work in this type.
- Apart from the physical aspects, the classroom works best when adequate amount of light, ventilation, and acoustical treatment is provided.

7 INFERENCE

Fig.7.1 Conceptual Diagrams (Source:-Author)

- No Classroom can be designed and repeated as a prototype the strategy varies as per site and surroundings
- Circulations of the informal spaces need to complement so as to come up with an ideal learning space. The learning spaces of junior colleges should be various typologies, the fact that no two subjects are similar justifies that this.
- Learning process related to theory should be dealt differently while, subjects with analytical understanding should be planned for discussions, group activities.
- Technology provided should be maintained and used.
- The Learning space can be reinterpreting in the 12th standard context, a classroom for theory lecture that opens into another space exclusively for practical knowledge promoting innovative teaching policies.

Table 7-1 Do's and Don'ts for a designer (Source:-Author)

Do's	Don'ts
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Furniture arrangement such that all the students are able to see the teacher and vice versa. • Comfortable for seating. • Audio –visual learning should be promoted. • The wall needs to be painted with a soothing colour such as light tints of blue, ivory etc. • For interaction and group activities, experiments, for English skits, geography; hall is ideal 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Isolated seating provisions create a disconnection during a lecture. • The seating should not have sharp edges. • The screen should be located such that the chalk board can also be used simultaneously. • Use of warm colours as they create a discomfort visually while learning. • Tiered class rooms for leanings of mathematics and similar theory subjects.

8 CONCLUSION

The research intended to study classrooms and the architectural response. The important consideration to our context is the intake of students, few institutes don't have enough space for expansion like Case 2 college, while few have controlled the student teacher ratio for better learning Example:-Case 4. It is not always feasible for all institutes to maintain these proportions due to factors like economy, student background, and intake demand. Thus few recommendations have been suggested to enhance these existing spaces.

The relationship of discipline, teaching learning mode and space has a strong relationship that needs to be considered by the designer. In case of the 11th and 12th classroom teaching learning process has remained the same in spite of the discipline, yet the designer must consider changing mode of teaching with technology, and each demand that can be foreseen with the change of curriculum. A holistic approach needs to be given to design a learning space. One can understand the impact evolution of education on architecture from the Table 2-1. Most subjects might be taught in same classroom configuration, the interaction with students and teachers revealed that they want no generic modules. The old institutes need to adapt to new requirements for which they can take inspirations from the new institute. The new institutes can also understand the success of old ones for better development for future.

8.1 SOME RECOMMENDATIONS

- From different case examples, the area per student should be 1.2-1.5sq.m per student in an Indian Context.
- The area of the classroom can be derived from the limit as explained in the figure 8-1
- It is recommended that one needs to consider the visibility of board from the last bench.
- With the developing technology, the need for designing classrooms is very essential; the time has come where architecture has to catch up. Only then can the learning spaces evolve sensitively and help India building its youth.

Fig. 8-1 Conceptual Diagrams (Source: - Author)

9 REFERENCES

1. Baker, Lindsay. A History of School Design and its Indoor Environmental Standards, 1900 to Today. 1090 Vermont Avenue, N.W., Suite 700, Washington, DC 20005-4950: National Clearinghouse for Educational Facilities, January 2012.
2. Bennett, Meegan. "Keep Them Coming Back: Learning Spaces With Student Appeal." September 22, 2015.
3. Miller, Herman. Learning Spaces Sketchbook. Michigan, Herman Miller, Inc., Zeeland, Michigan, L.2702, 2015, https://www.hermanmiller.com/content/dam/hermanmiller/documents/education/Learning_Spaces_Sketchbook.pdf. Accessed on 21/06/2016 at 9.30pm
4. G.Z. Brown and Mark DeKay. Sun, Wind and Light, Publication-2001 by John Wiley and Sons, Inc.
5. Syed Nurullah, J. P. Naik. History of Education in India. (Mumbai) Bombay: Macmillain and Company, 1943.
6. Alicia. "Design matters." Evolving learning spaces, April 21, 2015.
7. <http://www.fergusson.edu> accessed on 27/01/2016 at 9.48 AM.
8. <http://mitgurukul.com> accessed on 19/02/2016 at 2.07PM
9. <http://pune.fyc.org.in> accessed on 11/02/2016 at 10.00 AM.

10. <http://www.fastcoexist.com/3038207/5-way> accessed on 02/02/2016 at 11.59 AM
11. www.mmcc.co.in accessed on 18/02/2015 at 9.30AM.
12. NalandaUniversity article:-
<http://www.saylor.org/site/wp-content/uploads/2011/04/Nalanda.pdf> accessed on 6/01/2016 at 8.30pm
13. Kwek, S.H. (2011). Innovation in the Classroom: Design Thinking for 21st Century Learning. (Master's thesis). Retrieved from http://www.stanford.edu/group/redlab/cgi-bin/publications_resources.php accessed on 14/01/2016 at 10.00pm